

THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Saidova Dildora Farhod qizi

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Annotation. This thesis reveals the role of translation methods in teaching of foreign languages. The effective ways of translation and pedagogical values are highlighted as well.

Key words: translation, tool, foreign, learner, teaching, ability, target language, analysis, communicative, pedagogical purpose.

Description. Translation has always been the core of the controversies on whether it can be a valid and effective tool in foreign language learning. Until recently, translation was out of favor with the language teaching community. It was criticized because of the close association with traditional grammar translation. It is still ignored as a useful language learning tool because of being not a communicative activity that is not suited to the general needs of the language learner. Translation is considered as time-consuming, boring, and irrelevant.

However, in the last few decades there has been an increasing interest in the translation practice in the foreign language classroom. Recently foreign language teachers have been reviving the use of translation for different learning purposes. It was observed that translation activity could be used for pedagogical purposes along with other traditional language teaching activities.

Translation in foreign language classes is in the process of becoming a form of “pedagogical translation”, which is no longer viewed as an ineffective tool in language learning and is evaluated as a way to enrich learners’ competences. Students taught by using pedagogical translation are encouraged to practice reading, writing, vocabulary, grammar, speaking. One of the main aims of foreign language teaching is to develop the student’s ability to communicate in the target language.

Translation heightens language awareness. While translating students are focused on identifying differences in structure and vocabulary, they have to evolve strategies to deal with them and to negotiate the potential of both languages. The real usefulness of translation in foreign language classes lies in comparison of grammar, vocabulary, word order and other language points in the target language and the student’s mother tongue. Students are directly exposed to contrasting language systems of the target and the native languages. Therefore, the learners should be required to discuss and correct common mistakes.

Translation might provide a guided practice in reading. Before starting translating a text it should be read carefully and analyzed in detail to determine the contents in terms of what, how and why it is said. Careful text analysis improves students reading comprehension and promotes vocabulary development.

As translation is regarded a communicative activity, it involves communication between the teacher and the student. Learners are encouraged to discuss rights and wrongs as well as problems related to the translation task. On the one hand, students are involved in a conversation on the translation topic, which helps them strengthen their speaking skills. On the other hand, students are requested to talk to both the teacher and other learners, and through listening to both the lecturer and the students improve their listening skills.

Moreover, translation activities need not be used in isolation, but should be included in an inherent part of the language learning course.

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